

Appendix C: Additional distribution figures

Fig. C.1. KDE of the *Gaia* effective temperatures divided into the SIMBAD spectral classes. This includes all sources in the O/B/A/F catalogue for which the temperatures and spectral classes are available. The temperature axis is linear and cuts off above 35 000 K as there are very few targets above that.

Fig. C.2. Histogram of the *Gaia* effective temperatures divided into the SIMBAD spectral classes. This includes all sources in the O/B/A/F catalogue for which the temperatures and spectral classes are available. The temperature axis is logarithmic and temperature bins have equal width in log-space.

Fig. C.3. Logarithmically scaled tangential component of eccentricity as a function of orbital period and sum of scaled radii. Effective temperatures are indicated by the colour gradient. The grey dashed line indicates the dip in the orbital period distribution at 27 days. Systems with high and low eccentricity are shaded with different colour maps (left and right colour bars, respectively). The vertical scale is cut off below 10^{-5} .

Fig. C.4. Logarithmic distribution functions of the orbital period of eccentric and circular EB systems. This includes all 14 573 correctly characterised EBs. Each panel shows a different T_{eff} bin, for the dividing temperatures of 7000, 8000 and 10000 K. The overall distribution is grey, the distribution of systems of low eccentricity is orange and that of systems with high eccentricity is blue. Indicated on the circular distributions are the 5th percentile, the median, and the 95th percentile.

Fig. C.5. Logarithmic distribution functions of the orbital period of eccentric and circular EB systems. This includes all 14 573 correctly characterised EBs. Each panel shows a different T_{eff} bin, for the dividing temperatures of 7000, 8000 and 10000 K. The overall distribution is grey, the distribution of systems of low eccentricity is orange and that of systems with high eccentricity is blue. Indicated on the eccentric distributions are the 5th percentile, and the 25th percentile.

Fig. C.6. Logarithmic distribution functions of the scaled orbital separation of eccentric and of circular EB systems. This includes all 14 573 correctly characterised EBs. Each panel shows a different T_{eff} bin, for the dividing temperatures of 7000, 8000 and 10 000 K. The overall distribution is grey, the distribution of systems of low eccentricity is orange and that of systems with high eccentricity is blue. Indicated on the circular distributions are the 5th percentile, the median, and the 95th percentile.

Fig. C.7. Logarithmic distribution functions of the scaled orbital separation of eccentric and of circular EB systems. This includes all 14 573 correctly characterised EBs. Each panel shows a different T_{eff} bin, for the dividing temperatures of 7000, 8000 and 10 000 K. The overall distribution is grey, the distribution of systems of low eccentricity is orange and that of systems with high eccentricity is blue. Indicated on the eccentric distributions are the 5th percentile, and the 25th percentile.

Fig. D.1. Histogram of the effective temperature for the pulsators. From top to bottom: all EBs, g-mode pulsators only, p-mode pulsators only, hybrid pulsators

Appendix D: Additional pulsation figures

Fig. D.2. Histogram of the orbital period for the pulsators. The overall distribution is grey, the distribution of systems of low eccentricity is orange and that of systems with high eccentricity is blue. From top to bottom: all EBs, g-mode pulsators only, p-mode pulsators only, hybrid pulsators.

Fig. D.3. Two examples of the data reduction artefact in QLP, compared to the SPOC. Top: TIC 393672467, bottom: TIC 180974778. On the left are periodograms of amplitudes with in grey the original data, in blue the data minus harmonics, and in orange the final residuals. Red lines indicate the independent frequency of the highest amplitude. On the right are the light curves folded by the orbital period. The orange curve is a harmonic model of sinusoids based on multiples of the orbital frequency.

Fig. D.4. A selection of EBs from the g-mode (only) pulsators of variability. On the left are periodograms of amplitudes with in grey the original data, in blue the data minus the data minus harmonics, and in orange the final residuals. Red lines indicate the independent frequency of the highest amplitude. On the right are the light curves folded by the orbital period. The orange curve is a harmonic model of sinusoids based on multiples of the orbital frequency. From top to bottom the orbital period increases.

Fig. D.5. A selection of EBs from the p-mode (only) pulsators of variability. On the left are periodograms of amplitudes with in grey the original data, in blue the data minus harmonics, and in orange the final residuals. Red lines indicate the independent frequency of the highest amplitude. On the right are the light curves folded by the orbital period. The orange curve is a harmonic model of sinusoids based on multiples of the orbital frequency. From top to bottom the orbital period increases.

Fig. D.6. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for all pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are not in the g-mode pulsators. Same as Figure 10.

Fig. D.8. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for g-mode pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of g-mode pulsators that are not in the p-mode pulsators.

Fig. D.7. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for p-mode pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are not in the g-mode pulsators.

Fig. D.9. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for hybrids. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are also in the g-mode pulsators.

Fig. D.10. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for all pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are not in the g-mode pulsators. Same as D.6, but with a logarithmic frequency axis.

Fig. D.12. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for g-mode pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of g-mode pulsators that are not in the p-mode pulsators. Same as D.8, but with a logarithmic frequency axis.

Fig. D.11. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for p-mode pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are not in the g-mode pulsators. Same as D.7, but with a logarithmic frequency axis.

Fig. D.13. Histogram of the extracted significant frequencies in each temperature range for hybrids. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size to better view the lower densities at high frequency. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are also in the g-mode pulsators. Same as D.9, but with logarithmic a frequency axis.

Fig. D.14. Histogram of the extracted significant amplitudes in each temperature range for all pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are not in the g-mode pulsators.

Fig. D.16. Histogram of the extracted significant amplitudes in each temperature range for g-mode pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size. Included are just those targets in the group of g-mode pulsators that are not in the p-mode pulsators. The distributions of the two middle T_{eff} bins are statistically identical (p-value of 0.952), all others are significantly different (p-value $< 10^{-13}$).

Fig. D.15. Histogram of the extracted significant amplitudes in each temperature range for p-mode pulsators. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are not in the g-mode pulsators. The distribution of the lowest T_{eff} is significantly different from all others. The distribution of T_{eff} between 7000 and 8000 K is significantly different from the two higher ones with p-values of 0.0014 and 0.012, respectively. The two distributions of the highest temperature bins are not distinguishable (p-value 0.809).

Fig. D.17. Histogram of the extracted significant amplitudes in each temperature range for hybrids. Bins are scaled logarithmically in size. Included are just those targets in the group of p-mode pulsators that are also in the g-mode pulsators. All distributions are significantly different from each other (p-value $< 10^{-5}$).